

Science

MANAGEMENT OF GRUDHRASI WITH UNIQUE COMBINATION OF AYURVEDIC HERBAL KWATHA & AGNIKARMA

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Abstract

Today people are predisposed to various diseases based on their way of living and occupational habits called life style diseases. Orthopedic disorders are one of the mostly exposed to such life style habits. physical inactivity, wrong body posture, occupational posture, long sitting jobs, stresses activity, exposure to continue vibration, post-operative causes, gym, athletes muscular spasm are main contributing factors to orthopedic disorders.

One of the most common orthopedic health problems today is lower back pain which is accompanied most of the time by Sciatica. The present case study is successful Ayurvedic management of a case of “GRUDHRASI”.

Keywords: Grudhrasi; Unique Combination of Ayurvedic Herbal Kwatha; Agnikarma.

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1. Introduction

Ayurveda described sciatica as *Grudhrasi*. most of the common *Vata-vyadhi* observed in majority of people. *Grudhrasi* word itself describes the disease i.e. “*Grudhra*” (Eagle) like walking. The disease is caused by vitiation of *vata*, sometimes even *Kapha* vitiation along with *vata* also cause Sciatica.

‘*Grudhrasi*’¹ is a *Ruja pradhana Nanatmaja Vata Vyadhi*, intervening with the functional ability of low back & lower limbs. *Grudhrasi* cripple the life of patient by causing radiating pain (*Sphik-kati-prushtha-uru-janu jangha-pad kramgat vedana*) in leg while walking or rest as well.

The symptoms seen in *Grudhrasi* can be well correlated with “Sciatica” in modern terminology. Sciatica is a very painful condition in which pain begins in lumbar region and radiates along the postero-lateral aspect of thigh and leg. Hence, movement of the affected leg is restricted and

patient is not able to walk properly. It is particularly seen in most active period of life, involving working class people causing hindrance in routine life.

1.1. Case Report

The present case study is successful Ayurvedic management of a case of “GRUDRASI” (SCIATICA).

A 34 year old Male patient came to us with chief complaint of –

- 1) Pain radiating in the following manner –
- 2) *Sphik-Kati-Prishtha-Uru-Janu-Jangha-Pad Kramat Vedana.*
- 3) *Stambh*
- 4) *Toda*
- 5) *Muhurmuhu Spandana (Janu Kati Uru Sandhinam)*
- 6) *Deha Pravakrata*
- 7) *Pad Suptata.*

Patient had above complaints since last 1 month.

1.2. History of Personal Illness

The patient was normal one month back. Since then patient has been suffering from Pain radiating in the following manner - *Sphik-Kati-Prishtha-Uru-Janu-Jangha-Pad Kramat Vedana* (+++), *Stambh* (+), *Toda* (++) , *Muhurmuhu Spandana (Janu Kati Uru Sandhinam)* (+), *Deha Pravakrata* (++) , *Pad Suptata* (+). He had tried all kinds of pain killer medicines, but nothing provide relief from his problem, then he came to our hospital – Sheth Sakharam Nemchand Jain Ayurved Rugnalaya, Solapur. For better treatment we admitted him in Ipd section of *kaychikitsa* department.

ASTAVIDHAPARIKSHAN:

Nadi (pulse)=84/min.

Mala (stool)= *Asamyaka*

Mutra (urine)= Normal

Jeevha (tongue)= *Ishat saam.*

Agni = Normal

Shabda (speech)= Normal

Akruti= *Madhyama.*

Bala= *Madhyama.*

Koshtha= *Madhyama.*

Raktadaaba(B.P.) =120/70 mm of Hg.

1.3. Examination and Investigation

- *Sakthikshepana-nigraha²* (SLRT) examination has shown positive at 10 degree of left leg.
- X-RAY LS –spine has shown early Osteo-arthritic changes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Method

- Sampling: Simple random case study.
- Center of study: S.S.N.J.Ayurved Rugnalayan, Solapur.

2.2. Material

Meshashrungyadi kwatha given in dose of 16 ml with *Eranda sneha prakshepa* after food b.i.d. and *Agnikarma* with *lohashalaka* 2 sittings in 8 days.

Management involve -

- 1) Ayurveda herbal *kwatha*- *Meshashrungyadi Kwatha*³

Table 1: Showing internal medicine used in treatment

Sr.no.	Dravya name (latin name)	Dose
1.	<i>Meshashrungi</i> (<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i>)	1gm
2.	<i>Vidnaga</i> (<i>Embelia ribes</i>)	1gm
3.	<i>Gokshur</i> (<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>)	1gm
4.	<i>Ashwagandha</i> (<i>Withania somnifera</i>)	1gm
5.	<i>Eranda</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i>)	1gm
6.	<i>Bilwa</i> (<i>Aegle marmelos</i>)	1gm
7.	<i>Bruhati</i> (<i>Solanum indicum</i>)	1gm
8.	<i>Kantakari</i> (<i>Solanum surattense</i>)	1gm

Kwath Nirman vidhi:

Kwath Nirman done as per procedure described in *sharangdhara samhita*⁴. There are three methods explained in *Sharangdhar samhita* among them the method in which water is taken 8(i.e 64 ml) times than coarse herbal powder(i.e 8 gm) & then boiled till ¼th quantity(i.e 16 ml) of total remain be taken. The raw materials which are to be used are collected from ISO certified company S.S.N.J. Ayurved Rasashala, Solapur. Thus, the *Meshashrungyadi Kwath* prepared.

Dose : 16 ml twice in a day

Anupana : *Eranda taila* 10ml----- 20 ml BD

Aushadhi sevana kala: *Adhobhakt* (After Meal)

Agnikarma:

Agnikarma Sthan: “*Antarakandaragulpha*”⁵

Upkarana: *Lohashalaka*

PROCEDURE DONE WEEKLY i.e. two times

3. Observation & Result

Clinical examination of the patients revealed regression of Pain, *Stambh*, *Toda*, *Muhurmuhu Spandana* (*Janu Kati Uru Sandhinam*), *Deha Pravakrta*, *Pad Suptata* within 8 days.

Table 2: showing result of tretment (before and after)

SYMPTOMS	BEFORE TREATMENT	AFTER TREATMENT
<i>PAIN</i>	+++	NIL
<i>STAMBHA</i>	+	NIL
<i>TODA</i>	++	NIL
<i>MUHURMUHUR SPANDAN</i>	+	NIL
<i>DEHA PRAVAKRATA</i>	++	NIL
<i>PAD SUPTATA</i>	+	NIL

4. Discussion

The patient is PORTER by profession so long standing HARD WORK is leads to *hetu* of *grudhrasi*.

- 1) *Ahar*- improper and irregular diet,tea,cold drinks causes the disturbance of *tri-doshas*.
- 2) *Vihar*-long standing job, exertion immediatly after meal.
- 3) *vaya*- *Madhyam avastha*
- 4) *Mansika nidan*- *Atichinta,santapa*

SAMPRAPTI

Management involve -

1) MODE OF ACTION OF KWATH

Table 3: showing mode of action of kwatha⁶

Sr.no.	Dravya	Action
1.	<i>Meshashrungi</i>	<i>Shothahar,vedanahar</i>
2.	<i>Vidnaga</i>	<i>Nadisaunstan balya</i>
3.	<i>Gokshur</i>	<i>Vedanasthapan,vatshaman</i>
4.	<i>Ashwagandha</i>	<i>Mastishkashamak,Shothahar,vedanasthapan</i>
5.	<i>Eranda</i>	<i>Vatshamak,balya,vedanasthapan,angmardprashman</i>
6.	<i>Bilwa</i>	<i>Naditantu shamak,vedanashapan,shothahara</i>
7.	<i>Bruhatai</i>	<i>Vedanasthapan,dipan,pachan,grahi,krimighna</i>
8.	<i>Kantakari</i>	<i>Sadnya prabodhan, vatahar,Vedanasthapan</i>

2) MODE OF ACTION OF AGNIKARMA

In *Chikitsa* of *Grudhrasi* Ayurveda mainly concentrate on bringing back the viated vata dosha in the state of equilibrium. The Contents of *Meshshrungyadi kwatha* have *Dipan, Pachan, Vedanasthapan & Vat-shamak* properties⁶ which Helps in bringing back the viated doshas in the state of equilibrium along with *Agnikarma*.

1) *Upkarana:Lohashalaka*

2) *Agnikarma Sthan: "Antarakandaragulpha"*⁵

5. Conclusion

Since the therapy for *Grudhrasi* has limitation in other pathies, the unique combination of Ayurvedic herbs *kwatha* and *Agnikarma* can be effective therapy in *Grudhrasi*.

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